

ISic0069

I.Sicily inscription 0069

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [DivoCaesari]

2. [P(ublio)CornelioLicinioValeriano]

3. [filioImp(eratoris)Cae]s(aris) · P(ubli) L[iciniEgnati]

4. [Galli]eni · P[ro] Fel[ic]i[[is)Aug(usti)]

5. [frat]ri · P(ubli) · Licin[i]Salo]

6. [ni]ni · no[bilissimi Caes(aris) ---]

Apparatus

Text of

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491859

EDR 142431

EDCS 22100598

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7479 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650805>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 70

Fasolo, M. 2013. Tyndaris e il suo territorio. Volume 1. Introduzione alla carta archeologica del territorio di Tindari. Rome. At 77 no.12 fig.41

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